

Analysis of the Near-Substellar Brown Dwarf TOI-6285b

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ABSTRACT

Here we present results from TOI-6285b, a transiting brown dwarf (BD) orbiting a young A-type main sequence star. We used a global fit to derive the parameters of the host star, BD, and system as a whole. We found that the BD has a mass of $M_{BD} = 87.0^{+2.2}_{-2.1} M_J$ and a radius of $R_{BD} = 0.790^{+0.028}_{-0.022} R_J$. The host star has a mass of $M_* = 1.809^{+0.068}_{-0.067} M_\odot$, a radius of $R_* = 1.899^{+0.058}_{-0.038} R_\odot$, and an effective surface temperature of $T_{\text{eff}} = 7340^{+200}_{-210}$ K. From these parameters and the MIST model we calculate a stellar age of 540^{+180}_{-140} Myr. We derive an orbital period $P_{BD} = 6.85813 \pm 0.00001$ days and an eccentricity $0.0032^{+0.0024}_{-0.0020}$, suggesting a close orbit that may have been circularized. The BD lies far enough above the substellar transition point to be in an ambiguous position between very massive BDs and ultra low-mass stars, while its radius is extremely low for the age of the system. These characteristics raise interesting questions about the formation mechanism of TOI-6285b and the potential implications on the formation of similar objects in general.

1. INTRODUCTION

Brown dwarfs, objects that have historically been defined as more massive than planets yet less massive than hydrogen-burning stars, have been observed as companions around many stars in our galaxy, but the precise mechanism of their formation remains an unsolved problem in astrophysics. The range is generally defined as starting around $13 M_J$, where deuterium fusion becomes briefly possible, and ending around $80 M_J$ once hydrogen fusion becomes possible (Burrows et al. 2001). They have been observed singly and in binary pairs in interstellar space, but compared to planets they are inexplicably uncommon within orbital distances of 10 au (Sahlmann, J. et al. 2011; Softich et al. 2022). This so-called "brown dwarf desert" has closed slightly in recent years thanks

to the significant effort put into searching for low-separation brown dwarfs, but this deficit is still statistically significant and warrants explanation.

The driest part of the desert is located in the $30\text{-}55 M_J$ range. The brown dwarf size distribution appears to be bimodal on either side of this gap, suggesting that these two mass-distinguished brown dwarf populations have differing formation mechanisms (Unger et al. 2023). Authors have coalesced around two main processes: core accretion in the protoplanetary disk, resulting in a brown dwarf on the small end of the range, and gravitational instability amid the chaos of stellar formation, resulting in a larger brown dwarf. Core accretion in the disk, akin to the planetary formation process, could be efficient for BDs that form at a distance

greater than 0.5 au before migrating inwards, but it would be unlikely to provide enough mass for a BD larger than $40M_J$. Gravitational collapse as with a binary pair may produce a BD closer to the star but should certainly not impose an upper mass limit on any resultant BD, though a minimum mass could be expected from this pathway as the instability must be large enough to not simply merge with the primary (Šubjak et al. 2020). Furthermore, isolated BDs of masses comparable to the lower end of the desert have been reported to have isotope ratios hinting at a gravitational collapse formation pathway (Zhang et al. 2021).

As Carmichael et al. (2021) point out, then, it makes little sense to group these three distinct populations (high-mass companion BDs, low-mass companion BDs, and independent BDs) into a single monolithic category. Discerning the differences between and origins of these populations requires the careful study and characterization of as many BDs and ultra low-mass stars as possible.

Transiting BDs like TOI-6285b are particularly useful to this effort because they allow for the precise characterization of both the mass and radius of the dwarf, as we can observe the host star’s radial velocity with far greater accuracy (due to the fact that a transiting system must be nearly edge-on so $\sin i \approx 1$ and thus $v_r \sin i \approx v_r$) while also measuring the radius from the periodic dimming of the host star’s light in transit events. This, in turn, lets us check our models against our observations with far greater rigor.

Here we present data from TOI-6285b, a brown dwarf that is doubly interesting: its orbit is almost perfectly circular, raising the possibility of tidal circularization, and it is right at the substellar limit – evidence for a potential star-like formation.

2. OBSERVATIONS

2.1. *TRES Spectroscopy*

Table 1. Astrometric Properties of TOI-6285

Parameter	Description	Value
Position		
α	Right Ascension (hrs)	01 36 52.3
δ	Declination (deg)	51 37 53.7
π	Parallax (mas)	2.3418 ± 0.0137
Motion		
RV	System RV (km/s)	-27.972
μ_α	RA PM (mas/yr)	-0.2413 ± 0.0136
μ_δ	Dec PM (mas/yr)	-6.9085 ± 0.0121
Magnitude		
T	TESS T mag	10.6008 ± 0.0096
G	Gaia G mag	10.9949 ± 0.0004
WISE1	WISE1 mag	9.727 ± 0.023
WISE2	WISE2 mag	9.743 ± 0.02
WISE3	WISE3 mag	9.661 ± 0.044
WISE4	WISE4 mag	9.015

Spectra for TOI-6285 were taken using the Tillinghast Reflector Echelle Spectrograph (TRES), a high-throughput fiber-fed echelle mounted on the 1.5m telescope at the Fred Lawrence Whipple Observatory on Mount Hopkins, Arizona. TRES has a passband of 370 - 900 nm, and the largest fibers have a sky diameter of 3.45”, offering us a superb instrument for getting data from TOI-6285 with minimal contamination. We were fortunate with weather and obtained twelve good spectra from the night of September 3 through September 20. We experimented with multiple different exposure time settings ranging from 250s to 1200s. We ran all of our spectra through the Stellar Parameter Classification program (SPC) and a multi-order spectroscopy processing tool. The multi-order tool measured the redshifts of approximately 20 different spectral lines that were statistically distinct from an ideal spectrum to get more accurate radial velocity figures.

Figure 2. The lightcurve from the October 19, 2023 transit, processed with *AstroImageJ*. The blue points represent the normalized flux of TOI-6285, while the pink ones represent the normalized flux detrended according to the airmass factor (purple). The larger pink circles correspond to a 10x binning of the airmass-detrended normalized flux, and the green line represents a rough, *AstroImageJ*-provided fit for the transit. The airmass is scaled by an arbitrary negative value. The relative flux from comparison star C54 is in apricot, showing one of the constant lightcurves that TOI-6285 was compared against.

than KeplerCam, so a principal motivation of our use of KeplerCam was to confirm that the transit event was actually occurring in the TOI-

6285 system, instead of around another star in the TESS field.

3. ANALYSIS

3.1. Global Fit and Parameters

We used `RadVel` to run an early fit of the system and confirm that our radial velocity data was good enough to get results similar to those in the TESS Catalogue. Once we had access to `EXOFASTv2` there was no need for the `RadVel` run. We used parameters from the catalogue, GAIA DR3, SPC, and `AstroImageJ` as prior values for a global Markov Chain Monte Carlo fit with `EXOFASTv2` to model the parameters of the system given the data we collected, the TESS transit data, and a spectral energy distribution from WISE, GAIA, and TESS data.

Figure 3. Transit and radial velocity fits for TOI-6285b from `EXOFASTv2`.

Table 3. `EXOFASTv2` Starting Values

Parameter	Value	Source
M_* (M_\odot) ..	1.38	TESS Catalogue
R_* (R_\odot) ...	2.12	TESS Catalogue
T_{eff} (K)	6605	TESS Catalogue
π (mas)	2.37567	GAIA DR3
P (days) ...	6.8581311	TESS Catalogue
[Fe/H] (dex)	0.29 ± 0.06	SPC
R_P/R_*	0.053	<code>AstroImageJ</code>

3.2. Age of the TOI-6285 System

We used the built-in MIST modeling function of `EXOFASTv2` to model the age of TOI-6285 using stellar isochrones (Dotter 2016; Choi et al. 2016; Paxton et al. 2011, 2013, 2015). We derived a value of $0.54^{+0.18}_{-0.14}$ Gyr, which combined with the T_{eff} of the star suggests an early-F or late-A main sequence star. Given its close, low-eccentricity orbit around the star, TOI-6285b presumably formed around the same time.

Figure 4. MIST model fit from `EXOFASTv2`.

Table 4. EXOFASTv2 Fit Results

Parameter	Value
Stellar Parameters:	
M_* (M_\odot)	$1.809^{+0.068}_{-0.067}$
R_* (R_\odot)	$1.899^{+0.058}_{-0.038}$
$\log g$ (cgs)	$4.140^{+0.017}_{-0.030}$
L_* (L_\odot)	$9.5^{+1.1}_{-1.0}$
ρ_* (cgs)	$0.375^{+0.020}_{-0.035}$
T_{eff} (K)	7340^{+200}_{-210}
[Fe/H] (dex)	$0.301^{+0.052}_{-0.058}$
Age (Gyr)	$0.54^{+0.18}_{-0.14}$
A_V (mag)	$0.77^{+0.11}_{-0.12}$
π (mas)	2.376 ± 0.017
d (pc)	420.8 ± 3.0
Planetary Parameters:	
P (days)	6.858127 ± 0.000014
R_P (R_J)	$0.790^{+0.028}_{-0.022}$
M_P (M_J)	$87.0^{+2.2}_{-2.1}$
a (au)	0.0874 ± 0.0011
i (Degrees)	$89.09^{+0.65}_{-0.89}$
e	$0.0032^{+0.0024}_{-0.0020}$
T_{eq} (K)	1652^{+41}_{-40}
τ_{circ} (Gyr)	5960^{+850}_{-960}
R_P/R_*	$0.04273^{+0.00072}_{-0.00085}$
a/R_*	$9.91^{+0.17}_{-0.32}$
δ	$0.001826^{+0.000062}_{-0.000072}$
b	$0.16^{+0.14}_{-0.11}$
ρ_P (cgs)	219^{+18}_{-22}
$\log g_P$ (cgs)	$5.540^{+0.024}_{-0.030}$
$M_P \sin i$ (M_J)	$87.0^{+2.2}_{-2.1}$
M_P/M_*	0.04592 ± 0.00062

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Tidal Circularization

From EXOFASTv2 we derive $\tau_{\text{circ}} = 5960^{+850}_{-960}$ Gyr as an estimate for the circularization timescale of TOI-6285b. This is far older than the age of the system, so the EXOFASTv2 results suggest that this orbit has not been tidally circularized. However, with an eccentricity of

Figure 5. Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) over several passbands from EXOFASTv2, showing general concordance between the model (blue dots) and observations.

Figure 6. Probability density functions of several variables fitted EXOFASTv2, showing reasonable convergence around medians.

$e = 0.0032^{+0.0024}_{-0.0020}$ TOI-6285b's orbit is circular to a degree that other authors have invoked tidal circularization to explain (Jackson et al.

2008). It is possible that interactions in the protoplanetary disk may have circularized the orbit, or that the orbit simply began in a primordially circular state, but it is also possible that EXOFASTv2’s tidal circularization timescale may not reflect the specifics of this system.

To follow another approach, Šubjak et al. (2020) cite an expression from Jackson et al. (2008) that describes the timescale of the exponential decrease in the orbital eccentricity of a close-in-companion: $\frac{1}{\tau} = \left[\frac{63}{4} \sqrt{GM_*^3} \frac{R_{BD}^5}{Q_{BD} M_{BD}} + \frac{171}{16} \sqrt{G/M_*} \frac{R_*^5 M_{BD}}{Q_*} \right] a^{-\frac{13}{2}}$. In this expression, M_* , R_* , M_{BD} , and R_{BD} refer to the masses and radii of the star and the brown dwarf respectively, while G is Newton’s gravitational constant. Q_* and Q_{BD} are the tidal dissipation parameters of the star and the BD. Thus, the term involving Q_{BD} reflects the circularizing influence of stellar tides on the brown dwarf while the term involving Q_* is related to the influence of the brown dwarf’s tides on the star.

The main problem is characterizing the Q values, which is inherently difficult for a faraway system such as this. Šubjak et al. (2020) refer to past studies constraining $\log Q_{BD} > 4.15 - 4.5$, and authors have in the past chosen to use the value $Q_J \approx 10^5$ established by Lainey et al. (2009) as a proxy for the value of Q_{BD} . However, there remains substantial uncertainty on this front (Persson et al. 2019; Jackson et al. 2008). Q_* is similarly poorly-constrained, and Jackson et al. (2008) report that values from as low as 10^5 to as high as 2.25×10^9 have been found.

If we follow Šubjak et al. (2020) and Persson et al. (2019) in adopting values of $Q_{BD} = 10^5$ and $Q_* = 10^8$, we find that $\tau_{\text{circ}} \approx 54.3$ Gyr for TOI-6285b, substantially shorter than the EXOFASTv2 calculated circularization timescale but still vastly longer than the age of the system according to the MIST model.

Figure 7. Tidal Circularization Timescale of TOI-6285b as a function of Q_* and Q_{BD} . Q_* dominates the timescale for this system, and if we assume tidal circularization we must have $Q_* < 10^6$.

With the inherent uncertainty of the Q values in mind, however, we also used the equation given in Jackson et al. (2008) to generate a rough plot of the circularization timescale as a function of Q_* and Q_{BD} . We observe a strong dependence on Q_* , suggesting that the system may or may not be tidally circularized depending on the value adopted for Q_* (which is not strictly defined or known for this system). Specifically, any $Q_* < 10^6$ would result in a τ_{circ} comparable to the age of the system; as Lin et al. (1996) report $Q_* = 1.5 \times 10^5$ for main-sequence stars, this does not seem entirely unreasonable given the young age of TOI-6285.

It should be noted, however, that TOI-6285 has begun to evolve into a subgiant according to the MIST model; the star’s convective zone is starting to expand increasingly swiftly, so we are witnessing the result of cumulative effects over the star’s lifetime as Q_* (already uncertain) changes even further. Our nominal constraint on $Q_* < 10^6$ is presented as a neat demonstration of how circularized main-sequence systems might be used to constrain Q , but we cannot draw any firm conclusions here as there is simply too much uncertainty.

4.2. Tidal Synchronization

We derive a value of 16.1 ± 0.3 km/s for the rotation velocity of TOI-6285 using the SPC script (Buchhave et al. 2012). Given a stellar radius $1.899^{+0.058}_{-0.038} R_{\odot}$, this translates to a rotational period for the star of $5.97^{+0.21}_{-0.16}$ days. Nielsen et al. (2013) report a significantly smaller median value (less than four days, with a narrow distribution) for the rotation period of late A/early F stars in their analysis of Kepler stars, suggesting that the system may have undergone some tidal spin-orbit synchronization between the star and the BD – though again, our star is evolved and so some slowing would be expected. Equations exist for the synchronization timescale, but they are even less applicable in our case because TOI-6285’s rotation period and moment of inertia factor have changed substantially as it has evolved, to say nothing of Q_* (Šubjak et al. 2020).

The main conclusion from this line of tidal inquiry is that tidal circularization and synchronization may well be factors that explain some of the parameters of the TOI-6285 system, but they cannot be discussed with any degree of certainty. The optimal path forward in this area is likely to be observing more transiting BDs to assemble a dataset of comparable close-in dwarfs.

4.3. Parameters of TOI-6285b

Our derived parameters from EXOFASTv2 suggest that TOI is an extremely massive brown dwarf or very low mass star, with a mass of $87.0^{+2.2}_{-2.1} M_J$ and a radius of $0.790^{+0.028}_{-0.022} R_J$. Burrows et al. (2001) report that the substellar limit for objects of solar metallicity and helium ratio is $0.07 \sim 0.074 M_{\odot}$, increasing as metallicity decreases. The metallicity of TOI-6285 is $0.301^{+0.052}_{-0.058}$, substantially greater than solar. Additionally, orbiting bodies are generally metal-enriched compared to the central star in a system, suggesting that TOI-6285b might be even more metal-enriched (Bean et al. 2023).

This makes it highly likely that TOI-6285b is not merely a brown dwarf but an ultra low-mass star. For the sake of convenience, this paper will continue to refer to it as a brown dwarf.

If TOI-6285b is a stellar object, it should have by this point (~ 0.5 Gyr) stabilized onto the main sequence with a luminosity $L_{BD} > 10^{-4} L_{\odot}$ and a radius $R_{BD} \approx R_J$. The high metallicity has the effect of increasing the opacity of the dwarf’s atmosphere, blocking energy release from the core and resulting in a cooler effective temperature than for a zero-metallicity dwarf. For this reason, we might expect an effective temperature somewhere in the range of $T_{\text{eff}} \sim 2000$ K (Saumon et al. 1994; Burrows et al. 2001; Baraffe et al. 2002). Confirming this should be possible by observing TOI-6285 at a time opposite to the primary transit, and by searching for evidence of different transit depths at different wavelengths.

The radius of TOI-6285b is of special interest. At less than $0.8 R_J$, it is simultaneously one of the most massive known brown dwarfs while also having one of the smallest radii of any brown dwarf on record, despite being not even a billion years old (Carmichael 2022). This is a puzzle and suggests some issue with our models, some unique property of TOI-6285b (perhaps its high metallicity), or (perhaps more likely) an issue with the EXOFASTv2 run. This anomalously low radius is still perplexing if the BD is actually a hydrogen-burning star.

4.4. Conclusion

In conclusion, transiting brown dwarfs like TOI-6285b present a powerful opportunity to apply radial velocity spectroscopy and transit photometry to the characterization of objects that blur the lines between planets and stars. While we cannot say much more about the formation and evolutionary of the system, TOI-6285b is massive enough that it falls far to one side of the brown dwarf desert, and its origin is best explained through the star-like gravi-

Figure 8. Figure 4 from Carmichael (2022), with TOI-6285 added as a blue circle with a teal border. The BD is notably located well below even the 10 Gyr isochrones of both models, despite its host star being less than a billion years old.

tational instability pathway thought to be responsible for such massive objects (Šubjak et al. 2020). This makes sense; the BD is so massive that it may well be a star.

As new BD systems are discovered at an accelerating rate, the characterization of similar objects near the substellar transition may reveal trends in stellar, planetary, and orbital parameters that lend still more credence to the hypothesis that they form like stars. For now, TOI-6285 is a fascinating target: it is likely to be a product of the stellar formation pathway, and is possibly a star in its own right. Its observed density is also far greater than what would be expected for a brown dwarf of its relatively young age. Further observation and modeling are very much warranted.

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Software: AstroImageJ (Collins et al. 2017), EXOFASTv2 (Eastman et al. 2019), RadVel (Fulton et al. 2018), SPC (Buchhave et al. 2012)

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